

EVALUATION OF THE KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDES, AND HEALTH INFORMATION-SEEKING BEHAVIORS REGARDING GENERATIVE ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN HEALTHCARE AMONG MEDICAL STUDENTS OF EBONYI STATE UNIVERSITY, ABAKALIKI.

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Abstract

Background

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is about making computers and machines capable of performing tasks that usually require human intelligence, such as learning, solving problems, understanding language, recognizing things, and making decisions, often by learning from huge amounts of data to improve over time. Despite the growing influence of these technologies, there is a significant gap in research regarding the medical students' readiness to integrate generative AI into their future practice in Nigeria. This study aimed to evaluate the knowledge, attitudes, and health information-seeking behaviors of medical students at Ebonyi State University regarding generative AI.

Methods

A descriptive cross-sectional study design was employed. Data were collected using a self-administered semi-structured questionnaire divided into five sections. Data analysis was performed using IBM SPSS version 25.0, using Chi-square tests to determine associations between independent and dependent variables. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

Results

The mean age of the respondents was 22.5 ± 2.7 years, with 57.8% being male. Knowledge of generative AI (GAI) was low, with 126 (32.2%) of the respondents having good knowledge and 265 (67.8%) having poor knowledge. Sixty-two percent (62.4%) agreed that GAI would improve health care delivery, whereas 71.6% of the respondents reported using AI tools to seek health-related information.

Conclusion

There is high awareness of Generative AI among the respondents, driven largely by the popularity of ChatGPT, though technical understanding remains low. A definitive shift in health information-seeking behavior has occurred, with students prioritizing AI tools over traditional medical databases.

Keywords: *Generative AI, Medical Students, Health Information-Seeking Behavior, Artificial Intelligence.*

INTRODUCTION

For more than 50 years since the invention of computer systems, efforts have been put in place to see how computers can fit various simple to complex tasks to replace human efforts.¹ This has led to the creation of different computer programs with the goal of handling these complex tasks and reducing human error. As such, computer systems and programs are being designed to vary in their capacities and dynamics and are directed at specific purposes. These purpose-driven programs have been incorporated and used to achieve efficiency and improve productivity in various aspects of our routine daily tasks, such as navigation on land, sea, and air, facial detection, recognitions for security checks for crime surveillance, voice recognition and commands, use of text editors and auto-correct functions on our phones and computers, electronic payment platforms, medical diagnoses, military operations, agricultural and pharmaceutical tasks etc.¹ As technology advanced, it became possible to train these computer programs on different aspects of human life using large amounts of data, leading to the development of various forms of artificially intelligent programs. Such a list includes the use of various search engines, reference management tools, plagiarism detectors, language editing tools, and data management software, among others².

The term "artificial intelligence (AI)" was coined nearly 70 years ago to refer to the use of computers to imitate human reasoning. The first application of AI was in mathematics in 1956 when it was utilized for proving theorems³ Artificial intelligence (AI) is a field of computer science that mimics human intelligence in learning and solving problems⁴ Over the past few decades, AI has received unprecedented attention and has been touted as a gateway to the Fourth Industrial Revolution⁵

Recent advancements in artificial intelligence (AI), specifically the development of large language models (LLMs) with natural language processing (NLP) techniques, as seen in conversational chatbots like ChatGPT and Bard, have attracted global attention due to their ability to provide appropriate, coherent, human-like responses to questions across diverse knowledge domains.⁶ NLP, a crucial field in artificial intelligence (AI) focuses on the interaction between human language and computer systems. natural language processing algorithms are capable of analyzing and generating human language, making them valuable tools in various sectors⁷ This has changed the way information is interacted within different fields of life, such as education, security, and healthcare.

The introduction of AI into health care systems is reshaping the medical landscape by optimizing clinical decision-making, improving patient outcomes, and enabling predictive analytics. Generative artificial intelligence (GAI), a subset of artificial intelligence that creates new content by learning from existing data, is particularly transformative in health care. It can generate medical images, assist in the diagnosis of diseases, propose treatment plans, and predict patient trajectories.⁸

Medical education has long been tasked with preparing students to navigate evolving technologies. As AI becomes more integrated into clinical practice, medical students must not only grasp the theoretical aspects of AI but also develop the practical skills to implement and trust these tools in clinical settings. However, AI technologies, especially generative AI, are not static. The rapid evolution of these technologies poses a challenge for medical schools, as curricula must be continuously updated to ensure that students are adequately prepared for the future of medicine.⁹

Health-information-seeking refers to the ways individuals (or students) look for, use, and evaluate information relevant to health care decisions. These behaviors are crucial for medical students as they search for reliable and relevant knowledge to inform their education and practice.¹⁰

Due to their knowledge of diseases and the different sources of medical knowledge on the internet, medical students have a high rate of self-diagnosis and self-treatment. In this digital age, the number of medical students obtaining Internet-based health information is also increasing. Medical students use social media platforms the most to obtain health-related information.¹¹ Medical students in Italy and Romania use social media to research medical topics and find relevant academic content. More medical students in Canada seek drug information via mobile devices. The capacity of medical students to seek and evaluate pertinent online health information varies significantly, according to studies.¹¹ The emergence of digital health, including generative artificial intelligence (AI), has also created new paradigms in health-information-seeking behavior. Generative AI, such as ChatGPT, has shown high accuracy in its medical knowledge. A recent study found that ChatGPT could accurately answer biomedical and clinical questions on the United States Medical Licensing Examination at a level that approached or exceeded the passing threshold. Proving that Generative AI has knowledge that is on par with that of medical practitioners.

Understanding how these students engage with AI-based health care tools can provide insight into their potential use, ethical concern, and willingness to trust AI in health care contexts.¹² This research is important because the way students perceive and interact with AI technologies may influence how such technologies are adopted, regulated, and integrated into health care systems in the future.

Therefore, this study will evaluate the knowledge, attitudes, and health information-seeking behaviors of medical students related to generative AI in health care. By exploring these dimensions, the study aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of how students who are expected to become future health care professionals view generative AI

Problem Statement

Despite the growing influence of AI in healthcare, there is a significant gap in research regarding the knowledge and attitude of medical students toward generative AI and their health-information-seeking behaviors with respect to this technology, especially in Nigeria. While it is acknowledged that students are increasingly exposed to AI concepts, there is limited evidence to suggest that they fully comprehend the capabilities, limitations, and applications of generative AI healthcare.¹³ Most studies have focused on AI in general, overlooking the specific nuances and implications of generative AI.

Studies have indicated that medical students do not express significant concern or fear of replacement by artificial intelligence (AI) in their profession. However, some students may experience anxiety related to the possibility of being displaced by AI, which may discourage them from considering certain medical specialties.³ As medical students believe that generative AI would take over many non-procedural specialties in medicine, most notably the primary care specialties and radiology, AI would take over many medical specialties.

The study also examines the health information-seeking behaviors of future medical doctors who will be charged with diagnosing diseases, health promotion, and awareness. Hence, it is important to look at the means by which medical students obtain health information, especially about generative AI.

This is critical because medical students must understand not only the technical aspects of generative AI tools but also their ethical implications, limitations, and clinical applications. If students are unaware of or do not trust these technologies, their integration into health care systems could be hindered, limiting the benefits of these innovations.¹⁴ Furthermore, the way students access and evaluate information about generative AI is underexplored. Are students turning to peer-reviewed journals, digital platforms, or other informal sources to learn m Consider reviewing or deleting this word, depending on the context. Such words are called hedge words as they are used to reduce the certainty or directness of an argument. If used unnecessarily, it can lessen the impact of your message. Use such words selectively.

Or about these technologies? How do they evaluate this information's credibility and relevance?

Given that medical students will soon be expected to work alongside AI tools, understanding their current knowledge, attitude, and health information-seeking practices is crucial for determining how well-prepared they are for integrating AI into patient care.

Justification of this study

The rationale for investigating the knowledge and health-information-seeking behaviors of medical students about generative AI is multifaceted. First, AI is projected to play an increasingly pivotal role in clinical practice. For instance, AI-driven diagnostic tools, such as generative adversarial networks (GANs) for image generation, are already enhancing diagnostic accuracy in fields like radiology.¹⁵ The successful application of AI tools heavily depends on the ability of healthcare professionals to trust and understand the technology.

Second, medical students are expected to be future AI stewards in clinical settings. If they lack sufficient knowledge or experience in using these tools, there is a risk that their full potential will not be realized.

This gap in understanding could hinder the broader implementation of AI technologies, slowing down medical advancements.

Third, understanding how medical students seek information about AI is important for improving medical curricula. By identifying the sources that students trust and utilize, educational institutions can better tailor learning modules, incorporate AI-related content, and promote critical thinking about the role of technology in health care. If students rely on less reliable or biased sources of information, they may have a distorted understanding of AI, which may affect their clinical decision-making in the future.¹²

Finally, assessing students' engagement with AI will help health care systems and educational bodies identify the challenges and barriers students face in learning about these technologies. Addressing these gaps will ensure that future physicians are well-equipped to integrate AI into their clinical practice, fostering a health care system that maximizes the potential benefits of AI while mitigating its risks.

Given the exponential pace of AI development, now is the time to evaluate the readiness of medical students to use these technologies effectively. This research will not only enhance our understanding of students' preparedness but also inform the development of educational policies that ensure the next generation of healthcare professionals is ready for the challenges and opportunities posed by generative AI in healthcare.

General Objectives;

The main objective of this study is to evaluate the knowledge, attitudes, and health information-seeking behavior of medical students regarding generative AI in health care.

Specific Objectives;

1. Evaluate medical students' knowledge of GGA
2. Medical students' attitudes toward the use of generative AI in health care should be assessed, focusing on perception of trust and reliability.
3. Investigate the health information-seeking behavior of medical students in relation to generative AI, including their preferences for AI-driven health information sources.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Description of the study area

Ebonyi State is one of the five states that make up Nigeria's South East geopolitical zone. The geographical location of Ebonyi State is 6°15'N 8°05'E of the equator. It is bounded in the north by Benue State, in the south by Abia State and Imo State, in the west by Enugu State, and in the east by Cross River State. The state capital is Abakaliki, which is one of the Igbo speaking areas. Ebonyi State has three medical schools: Alex Ekwueme Federal Teaching Hospital, Ebonyi State University Teaching Hospital, and David Umahi Federal University Teaching Hospital. The study exercise was conducted among Ebonyi State University Medical Students, located in the Abakaliki metropolis.

Study Design

It is a descriptive cross-sectional study

Inclusion criteria

The inclusion criteria include all Ebonyi State University Medical Students.

Exclusion criteria

- Respondents who were absent from school on the data collection day
- Those who refused to provide consent for the study.

Determination of sample size

The sample size was calculated using the Cochran formula as follows:

$$N = Z^2 P(1-P)/E^2$$

Where:

- N is the minimum sample size,
- Z is the critical value of the normal distribution (1.96 for 95% confidence level),
- P is the estimated 50% prevalence
- E is the error margin (5%)

$$N = 384.16$$

Adding a 10 % (0.1%) non-response rate (r):

Here, N is the sample size adjusted for non-response

Therefore, our sample size adjusted for nonresponse (N) was 426 subjects.

Sample Technique used a stratified random sampling technique whereby the department of Medicine and Surgery was divided based on the different levels in the department (strata), and all levels (100 - 600) were proportionately allocated a sample size. Individuals in each level were then selected using a simple random sampling technique.

Tools for data collection

Data were collected using a sem-structured, self-administered questionnaire divided into five sections: A, B, C, D, and E. Section A includes the sociodemographic characteristics of the respondents, and Section B evaluates their awareness/knowledge Section C assesses their attitude focusing on trust and reliability perception Section D investigates their health information-seeking behavior, and Section E discusses the study's barriers and limitations.

Data collection procedure

The questionnaires were self-administered to the respondents, and the gray areas were corrected. Enough time was provided to answer the questions. There was no take-home, as all questionnaires were collected at the spot after filling out.

Data Management

Measurement of the variables

The variables of the study includes: Dependent and Independent variables. Independent variables include sociodemographic characteristics, such as age and gender. The dependent variables include knowledge/awareness,, attitudes, and health information-seeking behavior in relation to generative AI, including preferences for AI-driven health information sources. Awareness/Knowledge was assessed

using five multiple-choice question. The correct answer was awarded a score of 1, whereas the incorrect answer was awarded a score of 0. Finally, the summative score was obtained and converted into a percentage. Respondents who scored 50% were considered to have good knowledge. Attitude was assessed using four direct questions in a 5-point Likert format. Then, a mean score was obtained, and respondents who scored less than 2 were said to have a negative attitude.

Data Analysis

Statistical analysis was conducted using International Business Machine Statistical Product for Service Solution (IBM SPSS), version 25.0, to address the study's objectives.

Ethical Considerations

Several steps were taken to address the following ethical issues in this study:

1. Ethical Approval: Ethical approval for the study was obtained from the Ethics Committee of Ebonyi State University.
2. Informed Consent: The respondents were allowed to read and sign the informed consent by ticking for anonymity.
3. Voluntary Participation: Participation was voluntary, and respondents were assured that refusal to participate or withdrawal after consent did not result in victimization.
4. Confidentiality Assurance: Respondents were assured that all responses would be respected, kept confidential, and not tied to any identifying information such as their name, hence the precoding of the questionnaires.

RESULTS

A total of 391 questionnaires were properly filled and returned for analysis, which gave a response rate of 91.7%. The results of the analysis are presented in tables. The respondents were aged between 17 and 32 years, with a mean age of 22.5 ± 2.7 years.

Table 1: Respondents' sociodemographic characteristics (n=391)

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Age (years)		
<21	100	25.6
21-23	142	36.3
24-26	126	32.2
≥ 27	23	5.9
Mean \pm SD = 22.5 ± 2.7		
Gender		
Male	226	57.8
Female	165	42.2
Year of study		
100L	65	16.6

200L	60	15.3
300L	60	15.3
400L	83	21.2
500L	62	15.9
600L	61	15.6
Area of residence		
Urban	356	91.0
Rural	35	9.0

Table 1 shows that the respondents' mean age was 22.5 ± 2.7 years. The largest age group was those aged 21-23 years (36.3%), closely followed by 24-26 years (32.2%). There were more males (57.8%) than females (42.2%). The highest representation among the class levels was from the 400th level (21.2%).

Table 2: Awareness and Knowledge of Generative Artificial Intelligence

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Have you ever heard of generative artificial intelligence?		
Yes	339	86.7
No	52	13.3
How would you rate your general understanding of artificial intelligence?		
Excellent	84	21.5
Good	152	38.9
Fair	100	25.6
Poor	21	5.4
None	34	8.7
How familiar are you with the following generative AI tools?		
ChatGPT		
Not Familiar	51	13.0
Slightly Familiar	16	4.1
Moderately Familiar	43	11.0
Quite familiar	55	14.1
Very Familiar	226	57.8
Google Gemini		
Not Familiar	65	16.6
Slightly Familiar	38	9.7
Moderately Familiar	64	16.4
Quite familiar	67	17.1
Very Familiar	157	40.2

CoPilot		
Not Familiar	188	48.1
Slightly Familiar	65	16.6
Moderately Familiar	60	15.3
Quite familiar	38	9.7
Very Familiar	40	10.2
Midjourney		
Not Familiar	232	59.3
Slightly Familiar	51	13.0
Moderately Familiar	56	14.3
Quite familiar	27	6.9
Very Familiar	25	6.4
Grok		
Not Familiar	164	41.9
Slightly Familiar	42	10.7
Moderately Familiar	64	16.4
Quite familiar	52	13.3
Very Familiar	69	17.6
Meta AI		
Not Familiar	44	11.3
Slightly Familiar	33	8.4
Moderately Familiar	56	14.3
Quite familiar	64	16.4
Very Familiar	194	49.6
DeepSeek		
Not Familiar	159	40.7
Slightly Familiar	49	12.5
Moderately Familiar	53	13.6
Quite familiar	64	16.4
Very Familiar	66	16.9
Use of Generative AI in schools		
Answering medical questions		
Yes	297	76.0
No	94	24.0
Writing school assignments		
Yes	253	64.7

No	138	35.3
Generating medical case summaries		
Yes	127	32.5
No	264	67.5
Studying or revision		
Yes	250	63.9
No	141	36.1
None of the above		
Yes	20	5.1
No	371	94.9
Use of Generative AI in Health care		
Medical diagnosis		
Yes	154	39.4
No	237	60.6
Generate patient notes		
Yes	126	32.2
No	265	67.8
Predicting treatment outcomes		
Yes	115	29.4
No	276	70.6
Teaching/education		
Yes	236	60.4
No	155	39.6
None of the above		
Yes	47	12.0
No	344	88.0
Do you think medical schools should formally include AI and GAI training in their curriculum?		
Strongly Agree	134	34.3
Agree	122	31.2
Neutral	98	25.1
Disagree	27	6.9
Strongly disagree	10	2.6

Table 2 presents the self-reported knowledge and familiarity of medical students with generative AI. A significant majority of respondents (86.7%, n = 339) reported hearing of GAI. However, the largest group rated their general understanding of AI good (152, 38.9%). ChatGPT and Meta AI emerged to be the most

familiar tools with 57.8% and 49.6% of respondents reporting being very familiar with them, respectively.

Table 3: Attitude toward Generative AI in health care.

Variable	SD (n%)	D (n%)	N (n%)	A (n%)	SA (n%)
How do you feel about the use of generative AI in clinical decision-making?	17 (4.3)	45 (11.5)	157(40.2)	131(33.5)	41 (10.5)
I trust the information generated by the Generative AI	4 (1.0)	29 (7.4)	93 (23.8)	181(46.3)	84 (21.5)
GAI will improve health care delivery	5 (1.3)	19 (4.9)	123(31.5)	174(44.5)	70 (17.9)
GAI may replace doctors in the future	59(15.1)	99 (25.3)	106(27.1)	61 (15.6)	66 (16.9)
I feel confident in using GAI for medical tasks.	8 (2.0)	56 (14.3)	154(39.4)	131(33.5)	42 (10.7)
I have concerns regarding the ethical implications of GAI in medicine.	11(2.8)	38 (9.7)	125(32.0)	137(35.0)	80 (20.5)
GAI tools should only be used under professional supervision	11(2.8)	20 (5.1)	99 (25.3)	138(35.3)	123(31.5)

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Are you worried that generative AI could reduce your relevance in the medical profession?		
Yes	128	33.0
No	169	43.2
Not sure	93	23.8
Would you be comfortable using GAI as a doctor in the future?		
Yes	211	54.0
No	87	22.2
Not sure	93	23.8

Table 3 assesses the attitude of the medical students toward generative AI, using both a Likert scale and direct questions. There is an optimism that GAI will improve health care delivery (62.4% either agreed or

strongly agreed. However, the confidence in using GAI for medical tasks is lower than this optimism, as only 43.7% of the participants either agreed or strongly agreed.

Table 4: Health-Information-seeking behaviour of the respondents.

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Where do you usually seek health-related information? (Multiple Response)		
Google Search	198	50.6
ChatGPT or similar artificial intelligence tools	280	71.6
YouTube/Podcasts	162	41.4
Social media	53	13.6
PubMed/Google scholar	95	24.3
Medical textbooks and manuals	235	60.1
Others	32	8.2
How often do you use Generative AI to search for health or medical information?		
Daily	183	46.8
Weekly	61	15.6
Occasionally	126	32.2
Never	21	5.4
How accurate do you believe the health information provided by generative AI is?		
Very Accurate	57	14.6
Somewhat Accurate	232	59.3
Neutral	80	20.5
Inaccurate	15	3.8
I don't know	7	1.8
Which of the following best describes your trust in AI-generated health information?		
I trust it more than traditional sources	54	13.8
I trust it equally	194	49.6
I trust it less	134	34.3
I do not trust it at all	9	2.3
Have you ever verified AI-generated health information with other sources?		
Yes	246	62.9
No	30	7.7

Sometimes	115	29.4
Do you think that AI tools should be recommended as official information sources?		
Strongly Agree	46	11.8
Agree	118	30.2
Neutral	146	37.3
Disagree	59	15.1
Strongly Disagree	22	5.6

Table 4 shows that ChatGPT and other similar AI tools were the most frequently reported source of information (71.6%, n = 235). Medical textbooks and manuals remain highly used (60.1%). Nearly half of the respondents (46.8%) use GAI daily. The majority (62.9%) reported having verified AI-generated health information with other sources.

Table 5: Factors Affecting GAI Knowledge

Sociodemographic Characteristics	Good Knowledge	Poor Knowledge	X²	P value
Age				
Below 21	29 (29.0)	71 (71.0)	1.153	0.764
21-23	48 (33.8)	94 (66.2)		
24-26	40 (31.7)	86 (68.3)		
27 and above	9 (39.1)	14 (60.9)		
Gender				
Male	85 (37.6)	141 (62.4)	7.112	0.008
Female	41 (24.8)	124 (75.2)		
Year of study				
100 L	20 (30.8)	45 (69.2)	12.306	0.031
200L	10 (16.7)	50 (83.3)		
300L	17 (28.3)	43 (71.7)		
400L	33 (39.8)	50 (60.2)		
500L	20 (32.3)	42 (67.7)		
600L	26 (42.6)	35 (57.4)		
Area of residence				
Urban	121(34.0)	235(66.0)	5.664	0.017
Rural	5 (14.3)	30 (85.7)		

Table 5 shows that gender was statistically significant ($X^2= 7.112, p = 0.008$). Male students demonstrated a higher level of good knowledge (37.6%) than female students (24.8%). The level of study

year was also statistically significant ($p = 0.0031$). The highest percentages of good knowledge were found in the senior years: 600-level (42.6%) and 400-level (39.8%).

DISCUSSION

The respondents were aged between 17 and 32 years with a mean age of 22.5 ± 2.7 years. The sociodemographic characteristics of the study corroborate with other similar studies.

Regarding awareness, the majority (86.7%) of the respondents reported having heard of Generative AI. This is significantly higher than that of earlier studies, such as the systematic review on medical, dental, and nursing students' attitudes toward AI: a systematic review and meta-analysis conducted in Malaysia¹⁶, which noted that the majority of the students often had limited AI knowledge. The studies showed a high heterogeneity in awareness with differences in the participating countries.

ChatGPT was the most recognized tool (57.8%), followed by Meta AI (49.6%). This dominance of ChatGPT aligns with global trends, where OpenAI's model has become synonymous with GAI¹⁷. Conversely, tools such as Midjourney and Grok had low familiarity, which means that students are primarily focused on text-based LLMs relevant to academic and query-based tasks rather than image generation.

While awareness was high, only 21.5% of respondents rated their understanding of AI as "Very Good." The findings corroborated the findings of a systematic study on the integration of AI technology in deep learning to enhance university teaching and student learning processes²³. Among US medical students, where despite high interest, actual technical knowledge remained low.

A significant association ($p = 0.008$) was observed between gender and knowledge, with males demonstrating higher knowledge levels (37.6%) compared to females (24.8%). This corroborates the findings during a study; Artificial intelligence and the transformation of management education in Vietnam⁵ and in Nigeria during a study in Nigerian on Exploring Artificial Intelligence in the Nigerian Medical Educational Space: An Online Cross-Sectional Study of Perceptions, Risks and Benefits among Students and Lecturers from Ten Universities¹⁷, which also found gender gaps in AI familiarity. The findings revealed that 94.3% of the participants' demonstrated good knowledge, 77.0% exhibited positive attitudes, and 93.7% reported good AI practices. However, 82.1% had never heard of AI before the study, and 73.4% were unaware of its medical applications. More than half of the participants (54.6%) recognized AI as essential in the medical field, while 48.7% supported its inclusion in the medical curriculum. Additionally, 90.1% of the respondents had used AI in various domains, and 93.1% found it beneficial in simplifying tasks. Although most medical students demonstrated strong knowledge, positive attitudes, and appropriate practices regarding AI, gaps in understanding its medical applications underscore the need to integrate AI education into medical curricula. Enhancing AI awareness and training among future health care professionals is also crucial for improving adoption and use in clinical practice.

In this study, the 400L and 600L students demonstrated significantly higher knowledge ($p = 0.031$). This is expected because senior students are likely to use these tools more frequently for clinical case summaries and complex queries, as indicated in Table 2 (32.5% use it for case summaries). The urban

residents had significantly better knowledge ($p = 0.017$) than the rural residents. This reinforces the impact of infrastructure (electricity and internet access) on digital literacy, a challenge highlighted in the Nigerian context regarding infrastructural decadence.¹⁸

On attitude, 62.4% (Agree + Strongly Agree) believed that GAI would improve health care delivery. This aligns with the findings of Attitudes, readiness, and predictors of AI adoption among undergraduate medical students in India¹⁹, where students felt that AI would play an important role in health care. The fact that few respondents agreed that GAI might replace doctors in the future opposed the findings in Iraq on Solutions and the role of AI with its contribution to solving water problems to achieve sustainable development in Iraq²⁰, where two-thirds of students claimed AI would replace healthcare professionals. However, 33.0% of EBSU students explicitly stated they were "worried" that GAI could reduce their relevance. This anxiety reflects the broader global debate on AI redundancy and highlights the need for curricula that emphasize AI as a tool for augmentation rather than replacement³.

While 54.0% stated they would be comfortable using GAI as a doctor, 55.5% (Agree + Strongly Agree) expressed concerns about ethical implications. This mirrors the findings²³, where over 60% of students were worried about ethics. This implies that EBSU students are engaging critically with the technology, not just blindly accepting it.

One of the most profound findings of this study is the shift in information-seeking behavior, whereby 71.6% of students reported using ChatGPT or similar AI tools to seek health-related information, significantly outpacing Google Search (50.6%) and PubMed/Google Scholar (24.3%). This represents a fundamental change in how medical students act as "information foragers." The ease, speed, and conversational nature of AI will be trumping the rigorous but time-consuming process of traditional database searching.

Despite its high usage, blind trust is not absolute. Only 13.8% of respondents trust AI more than traditional sources, while 49.6% trust it equally. Crucially, 62.9% of the students reported verifying AI-generated information with other sources. This "trust but verify" approach is a positive sign of digital literacy, contrasting with the potential risk of "AI hallucinations" ⁶.

Most students (59.3%) viewed AI information as "Somewhat Accurate," rather than "Very Accurate." This skepticism aligned with the findings of the study "Attachment Intelligence Enables the Connotation, Dilemma and Path of High-Quality Development of Higher Education in China²¹ which noted that users often separate their trust in the technology from their trust in the specific information it provides.

Conclusion

The findings showed widespread awareness of generative AI, driven largely by the popularity of ChatGPT. However, the technical understanding of how these models work remains moderate, implying that students are consumers rather than informed users of the technology. There is a definitive shift in health information-seeking behavior; Generative AI has surpassed traditional databases, such as Google Search and PubMed, as a primary source for quick information among students. While efficiency is the driver, this

raises concerns about the information's depth and evidence base. Students generally view AI as a tool that will improve health care delivery and are open to using it in the future. However, significant ethical concerns and a fear of professional redundancy (being replaced) temper this optimism. There are significant disparities in AI knowledge based on gender and area of residence. Male students and those living in urban areas are currently better positioned to leverage these tools, creating a potential inequality in future professional readiness.

Recommendations

1. The College of Health Sciences should formally integrate an "AI in Medicine" module into the curriculum. This should not only be technical but should also focus on prompt engineering, verification skills, and ethics.
2. Student associations and the Faculty should organize workshops and seminars specifically for all students, with an emphasis on inclusive participation to bridge the knowledge gap between male and female students.
3. To address the urban/rural divide, the university should consider providing institutional access to premium, medically-tuned AI tools (if available) or robust internet access within the campus library to ensure that all students, regardless of residence, have equal access to these learning resources.
4. As students often look to mentors, faculty members must also be trained on GAI so they can guide students on its appropriate use rather than banning it or ignoring its existence.
5. The university should develop a clear "Acceptable Use Policy" for Generative AI in assignments and research. This will clarify boundaries, reduce academic dishonesty, and encourage responsible use.

Limitations of the Study

1. **Self-Reported Data:** The study relied on self-reported knowledge and behaviors, which may be subject to bias (e.g., students overestimating their understanding).
2. **Cross-Sectional Design:** The study captures a snapshot in time. Given the rapid evolution of AI (e.g., the release of GPT-4o or Gemini 1.5), students' knowledge and attitudes may change very quickly.
3. **Single Institution:** The study was limited to Ebonyi State University, and the findings may not be fully generalizable to students in other regions with different levels of technological exposure.

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